

Calibration of Atomic Force Microscope Probes using A Pneumatic Micromanipulation System

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Abstract—This paper presents an easy-to-use and efficient implementation of the added mass method for calibrating various atomic force microscope (AFM) probes without damage to the probe, which is based on the added mass method. The method is achieved by using a pneumatic control system and a home-made glass micro-pipette. Compared with the conventional added mass method, this method achieves the operation of the loading mass by negative pressure rather than the capillary force/electrostatic force, which is more stable and reliable. Therefore, it is efficient and reliable for placing/removing the loading mass to/from the AFM probe. It is a major significance for the calibration of unconventional shape cantilever. To confirm its ability, the polystyrene (PS) sphere is used as the loading mass to calibrate various AFM probes. The above experimental results show that this method can accurately and conveniently calibrate various AFM probes with less time consuming.

Index Terms—atomic force microscope probe, calibration, added mass method, pneumatic control system, micro-pipette.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since atomic force microscope (AFM) has been invented [1], it has been widely used to measure the various interactions between the probe and sample, so as to study the various characteristics of the sample. For instance, the study of cell mechanics [2], the elastic modulus of polymers [3], [4], and the adhesion force between the virus and cells [5]. The force sensor (AFM probe) plays a critical role in the experiment of measuring micro-/nano-forces. However, due to the limitations of micromachining technologies, manufacturers cannot accurately control the dimensions of the probe. And the probes are made from a variety of materials, such as silicon [6], silicon dioxide or silicon nitride [7] and polymer [8], [9]. In addition, for the purpose of conducting (i.e. Cr-Au, Cr-Pt, diamond) or improving their reflectivity (i.e. Au, Al) and their hardness of tip (i.e. diamond), many probes have a metal coating. For the above reasons, it is difficult to precisely guarantee the stiffness of the probe and the manufacturer generally only gives a range of stiffness of the probe. Stiffness of probe is closely related to the force measured. So, it is necessary to calibrate the stiffness of the probe before doing the experiment.

So far, calibration methods are generally divided into three categories:

1) *Dimensional models*: In dimensional models, the stiffness of the probe is obtained by theoretical calculation [10], [11] or finite element analysis [12], which depends on the dimensions of the probe (length, width, thickness), material

parameters (elastic modulus), etc. But it is difficult for many probes to accurately obtain these parameters, such as silicon nitride probe, probe with a coating and unconventional shape probe.

2) *Static methods*: Hooke's law is the basic principle of static methods. It has two key points: 1) apply a known force to the probe by attaching a sphere to probe [13] or the reference probe [14] and 2) measure the corresponding deformation of the probe. It is complicated and time-consuming.

3) *Dynamic methods*: The commonality of the dynamic method is need for high-speed measurement of the resonant frequency of the probe. In addition, the thermal fluctuations method needs high precision temperature control [15]. The unloaded resonant frequency method depends on the dimensional accuracy and the effective mass of probe [16]. The Sader method depends on the shape of the cantilever and requires dimensions, quality factor, and so on [17]. The added mass method obtains the stiffness of the probe by measuring the resonant frequency change of the probe before and after loading the mass [18], [19]. It requires few parameters (the resonant frequency and the quality of mass). Its main shortcomings are time consumption and the quality uncertainty of mass.

To sum up, all the calibration methods have their advantages and disadvantages. However, as the probe becomes more and more unconventional, a universal calibration method is an urgent need. So, the benefits of added mass method is more prominent: it does not harm the probe and is not dependent on the shape of the probe. In this paper, the added mass method is performed by using a pneumatic control system on a dual probe AFM system. The problem of time consumption is effectively compromised through reliable pneumatic control. In addition, the measurement accuracy can be improved effectively by selecting the appropriate loading quality. The technique can be implemented to an unconventional shape cantilevers.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE ADDED MASS METHOD

A. Principle of the added mass method

The added mass method is also called the Cleveland method because it was invented by Cleveland [18]. It is based on the following approximate formula:

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{M + m^*}} \quad (1)$$

where f , k and m^* are resonant frequency, stiffness and effective mass of the probe, respectively. M is a concentrated mass applied to the end of the cantilever, which is usually a standard sphere.

According to equation (1), the resonant frequency of the probe will vary with the adding mass. By taking the resonant frequency of the probe before and after adding mass and the added mass to formula (1), the following two formulas can be obtained:

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m^*}} \quad (2)$$

$$f_1 = f_0 + \Delta f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{\Delta m + m^*}} \quad (3)$$

where f_0 is the original resonant frequency without the added mass ($M = 0$), f_1 is the corresponding resonant frequency after adding a mass ($M = \Delta m$), Δf is the change of resonant frequency after adding a mass and Δm is an additional mass.

By combining formula (2) and (3), the stiffness (k) and effective mass (m^*) of the probe can be calculated:

$$k = \frac{4\pi^2 \Delta m}{1/f_1^2 - 1/f_0^2} = \frac{4\pi^2 f_0^2 f_1^2 \Delta m}{f_0^2 - f_1^2} \quad (4)$$

$$m^* = \frac{f_1^2 \Delta m}{f_0^2 - f_1^2} \quad (5)$$

Note that, the stiffness (k) of each point on the cantilever varies monotonically with the distance from the fixed end of the cantilever to the corresponding point. Therefore, the placement of the added mass is of great importance. The stiffness of the tip (k_{tip}) can be corrected by the following formula:

$$k_{tip} = k \left(\frac{L_m}{L_{tip}} \right)^3 \quad (6)$$

where k is obtained by formula (4), L_m and L_{tip} are the distance from the mass and the tip to the fixed end of the cantilever, respectively.

B. Choosing of loading mass

For added mass method, the choosing of loading mass is very important. Firstly, the diameter of the sphere cannot be too large. Otherwise it will affect the incidence or reflection of laser. Then, the quality of mass is moderate to cause sufficient frequency shift (Δf) and prevent it from moving during the measurement.

Common AFM probes are shown in Fig. 1. Their shapes are varied. As shown in Table I, their stiffness ranges from 0.06 to 45 N/m. The effective mass of the probe (m^*) can be obtained by putting the parameters provided by the manufacturer into the formula (2), which is from 0.60 ng to 10.16 ng. So, polystyrene (PS) sphere with diameters of 10 μm or 20 μm is considered to be used as loading mass. Their quality is 0.55

ng and 4.40 ng, respectively. When the inertia force of the PS sphere is less than the adhesion force between the PS sphere and cantilever, it can be guaranteed that the PS sphere does not move in the experiment.

Fig. 1. Optical images of the types of cantilever used in this work. (a) PPP-BIS, NanoSensors. (b) PPP-FMR, NanoSensors. (c) 160AC-NA, OPUS. (d) ATEC-NC, NanoSensors. (e) SCANASYST-AIR-HR, Bruker. (f) qp-BioAC, NanoSensors. (g) qp-BioT, NanoSensors. Scale bar: 20 μm .

TABLE I
THE PARAMETERS OF THE PROBE USED IN THIS WORK.

Type	f_0^1 (kHz)	k^1 (N/m)	m^* (ng)
PPP-BSI	28	0.1	3.23
PPP-FMR	75	2.8	12.61
160AC-NA	300	26	7.32
ATEC-NC	335	45	10.16
SCANASYST-AIR-HR	130	0.4	0.60
qp-BioAC-2	50	0.1	1.01
qp-BioAC-3	30	0.06	1.69
qp-BioT-1	50	0.3	3.04
qp-BioT-2	20	0.08	5.07

¹ f_0 and k are provided by the manufacturer.

1) *Inertia Force*: the inertia force of the PS sphere in the experiment can be calculated by the following formula:

$$F_{int} = m\omega^2 A \quad (7)$$

where m is the quality of the PS sphere, ω and A are the angular frequency ($\omega = 2\pi f$) and amplitude of the shock, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 2, the inertia force of PS sphere was calculated at the maximum amplitude of 20 nm and the maximum frequency of 350 kHz. The maximum inertia forces are 53 nN and 425 nN, respectively.

Fig. 2. (a) and (b) are the inertia forces when the diameter of PS sphere is $20 \mu\text{m}$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The maximum amplitude and the maximum resonant frequency are 20 nm and 350 kHz , respectively.

2) *Adhesion Force*: the adhesion force between the cantilever and PS spheres can be approximated using the Johnson-Kendall-Roberts (JKR) [20] model:

$$F_{ad} = \frac{3}{2} \pi \bar{R} W \quad (8)$$

where \bar{R} is the relative radius of curvature, W is the work of separating the two contact surfaces, and they can be expressed as follows:

$$\bar{R} = \frac{R_1 R_2}{R_1 + R_2} \quad (9)$$

$$W = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} = 2\sqrt{\gamma_1 \gamma_2} \quad (10)$$

where R_1 and R_2 are the curvature radius of the two contact surfaces, γ_1 and γ_2 are the surface energies of material 1 and material 2, and γ_{12} is the interfacial energy of material 1 and material 2.

Considering that the surface of the cantilever may have a metal coating, the adhesion forces between the PS sphere and different material (Si, Al and Au) were calculated, respectively. As shown in Table II, the adhesion force between the PS sphere with a diameter of $10 \mu\text{m}$ and cantilever is much greater

than the inertia force given in Fig. 2. But, in practice, the adhesion force is affected by many factors, such as relative humidity, surface evenness and surface contamination. The actual adhesion force may be greater and also be less than the calculated value, so it is very necessary to directly measure the adhesion force.

TABLE II
THE ADHESION FORCE BETWEEN THE PS SPHERE AND CANTILEVER.

	Si	Al	Au
Surface Energy (mJ/m^2)	1400 ^[21]	1100 ^[21]	2192 ^[22]
Adhesion Force ¹ (μN)	12.09	10.71	15.13

¹ The surface energy of PS is 47 mJ/m^2 [23].

As shown in Fig. 3, the same PS sphere (its diameter is $10 \mu\text{m}$) was used to measure the adhesion force between it and the different cantilever surfaces (Si, Al and Au). The fitting results illustrate the adhesion force between the PS sphere and silicon, aluminum and gold cantilevers are $2.70 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{N}$, $2.34 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{N}$ and $4.24 \pm 0.14 \mu\text{N}$, respectively. These forces are lower than theoretical calculations. The reason for this manifestation may be that the surface of the cantilever and the PS sphere is not ideal, so that their actual contact area is less than the theoretical contact area. But they are still much larger than the inertia force (53 nN).

Fig. 3. The histogram and fitting results (with the Gaussian function) of adhesion force between the PS sphere with a diameter of $10 \mu\text{m}$ and surface with three different materials (Si, Al and Au).

In addition, it is necessary to have an apparent frequency shift before and after loading mass. The frequency shift was estimated by putting the parameters of the probe (given in Table I) and the quality of the PS sphere to formula (3). Table III shows the minimum frequency shift is 1.00 kHz , which is very easy to be measured by the existing lock-in amplification technology. So, the PS spheres with a diameter of $10 \mu\text{m}$ or $20 \mu\text{m}$ were utilized to calibrate the AFM probes in this paper.

TABLE IV
PNEUMATIC COMPONENTS AND THEIR PARAMETERS

Name	Company-(Type)	Set pressure range (kPa)
Vacuum pump	LINICON-(LV125-V1007-A2-0001)	—
Air compressor	OUTSTANDING-(OTS-800X2)	—
Solenoid Valve	SMC-(VKF-332V-5G-M5)	—
Air Suction Filter	SMC-(ZFA100-01)	—
Precision Regulator	SMC-(IR1000-01)	5~200
Vacuum Regulator	SMC-(IRV10)	-100~-1.3
High-Precision Digital Pressure Display	SMC-(ZSE40F-01-62L)	-100~100

TABLE III
THE FREQUENCY SHIFTS FOR DIFFERENT PS SPHERE. (UNIT: KHZ)

Type	Δf_1 (10 μm)	Δf_2 (20 μm)
PPP-BSI	2.12	9.78
PPP-FMR	1.58	10.42
160AC-NA	10.67	62.91
ATEC-NC	8.71	55.15
SCANASYST-AIR-HR	36.11	84.97
qp-BioAC-2	9.74	28.36
qp-BioAC-3	3.94	14.20
qp-BioT-1	3.99	18.04
qp-BioT-2	1.00	5.37

III. EQUIPMENT AND EXPERIMENTS

A. Equipment

As shown in Figure 4 (a), the added mass method is performed by a pneumatic control system on a dual probe AFM system [24]. It mainly includes a pneumatic control circuit, a dual probe operating platform and a sine frequency sweep module. The probe is actuated by a sine sweep signal given from the sine frequency sweep module and its amplitude can be measured by a lock-in amplifier to obtain the resonant frequency of the probe. The PS sphere is operated by a home-made glass micro-pipette connected to the pneumatic control system. The precision control (pick and release) of the PS sphere is achieved reliably and efficiently by the pneumatic control system.

Figure 4 (b) shows the detailed description of the pneumatic control. It includes a positive pressure circuit and a negative pressure circuit, respectively. The pressure of the operating terminal (micro-pipette) is achieved by switching between the solenoid valve-I and solenoid valve-II. For example, when a negative pressure suction is required, the solenoid valve-I is opened and the solenoid valve-II remains closed. The specific parameters and information of pneumatic components are shown in Table IV.

B. Working Principle

As shown in Figure 5, the following experimental steps are mainly included:

- 1) A clean and isolated PS sphere is selected. When the micro-pipette is close to the PS sphere, the PS sphere is sucked by turning on negative pressure control. First, the IRV10 is set to the minimum. Then, the solenoid valve-I is opened. Finally, the negative pressure is slowly increased until the PS sphere is adsorbed to the front

Fig. 4. (a) Schematic diagram of experimental setup including a pneumatic control system is integrated into the dual probe AFM system. (b) The working principle of the pneumatic control. The solenoid valve-I and solenoid valve-II are initially closed.

of the micro-pipette. Normally, the negative pressure is increased to -80 kPa to ensure that the PS sphere can be stripped from the substrate.

- 2) The laser is adjusted to the front of the cantilever. The resonant frequency (f_0) of the probe is monitored by the sine frequency sweep module.
- 3) The micro-pipette is adjusted to be slightly higher than the cantilever and the PS ball is aligned with the front of the cantilever. Then the micro-pipette drop slowly, until it comes into contact with the cantilever by visual feedback. The negative pressure is switched to the positive pressure and the typical value of the high-precision digital pressure display-II is 0.06 kPa. Finally, the micro-pipette is slowly moved away from the PS sphere. It is caused by the positive pressure and adhesion between the PS sphere and cantilever.
- 4) The laser is again adjusted to the front of the cantilever to measure the resonant frequency (f_1).
- 5) The micro-pipette is close to the PS sphere at the front of the cantilever and the negative pressure of micro-pipette

is reopened to remove the PS sphere from the cantilever.

Fig. 5. Experimental procedure: (a) Pick up a PS sphere from substrate, (b) Measure the resonant frequency (f_0) of the probe without the loading mass, (c) Place the PS sphere to the cantilever, (d) Measure the resonant frequency (f_1) of the probe with the loading mass, (e) Remove the PS sphere from the cantilever. Scale bar: 20 μm .

After the above steps, the calibration of the probe is completed. And the PS sphere is still in the front of the micro-pipette, which can still be employed to calibrate the next probe. It takes about 10 minutes to calibrate a probe.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to verify the ability of the proposed method, seven probes (See Fig. 1) are calibrated in this paper. Firstly, for estimating the error of the proposed method, the PPP-BSI and PPP-FMR are calibrated, whose precise stiffness is supplied by manufacturer. Table V gives the calibration results and errors of the PPP-BSI. Its typical value is 0.1 N/m, which has a lot of deviation from the measured value. The deviation is mainly derived from the thickness error of the cantilever. The thickness of the cantilever increases as the stiffness of the probe increases, so it is more easily controlled when the stiffness of the probe is large (≥ 1 N/m). As shown in Table VI, the typical values (2.8 N/m) of PPP-FMR and the measured value are very close.

The calibration errors of PPP-BSI are 1.92 % to 16.36 %, whose average value is 7.07 %. However, the calibration errors

TABLE V
THE CALIBRATION RESULTS FOR PPP-BSI. (UNIT: N/M)

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Added mass	0.057	0.051	0.050	0.063	0.092	0.069
k_{quoted}	0.052	0.052	0.051	0.066	0.11	0.075
Error (%)	9.62	1.92	1.96	4.55	16.36	8.00

k_{quoted} is provided by manufacturer.

TABLE VI
THE CALIBRATION RESULTS FOR PPP-FMR. (UNIT: N/M)

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Added mass	2.88	2.75	2.83	2.75	2.65	2.75
k_{quoted}	2.80	2.80	2.80	2.70	2.60	2.80
Error (%)	2.86	1.79	1.07	1.85	1.92	1.79

k_{quoted} is provided by manufacturer.

of PPP-FMR are 1.07 % to 2.86 %, whose average value is 1.88 %. The latter is significantly smaller than the former. The reason for this phenomenon is that the resolution of the resonant frequency measurement is usually several hertz (the proposed method is 5 Hz). So, the absolute error is close, but the relative error is quite different.

As the experimental requirements continue to improve, a variety of unconventional shape cantilevers are designed. For instance, the SCANASYST-AIR-HR is produced to achieve high-speed scanning and the qp-BioAC/qp-BioT is produced to reduce the stiffness of the probe. Therefore, most of the conventional probe calibration methods are not applicable to it. Nonetheless, the added mass method is still feasible, which does not depend on the shape of the probe. As shown in Table VII, several unconventional shape cantilevers were calibrated. Compared with the typical value provided by the manufacturer, the maximum deviation is close to 30 %. So, it is necessary to carry out the calibration of the probe before doing the experiment.

TABLE VII
THE CALIBRATION RESULTS FOR THE SAMPLE PROBE. (UNIT: N/M)

	1	2	3	4
160AC-NA	26.70	24.39	25.17	24.97
ATEC-NC	46.57	44.93	49.96	42.52
SCANASYST-AIR-HR	0.416	0.374	0.399	0.408
qp-BioAC-2	0.107	0.118	0.083	0.103
qp-BioAC-3	0.051	0.058	0.073	0.062
qp-BioT-1	0.318	0.276	0.324	0.328
qp-BioT-2	0.073	0.111	0.109	0.086

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the added mass method is implemented by using a pneumatic control system. It is highly efficient and reliable to achieve the micromanipulation of PS sphere by a home-made micro-pipette connected to a pneumatic control system. It overcomes the randomness and uncontrollability of microspheres using capillary force/electrostatic force to manipulate it. Calibration of each probe takes about 10 minutes. Its real novelty is that it can quickly and harmless calibrated

the AFM probe with an unconventional shape. And it do not need to take into account the coating and material of the probe.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is supported in part by the National Natural Science Foundation of China under Grants 61573121 and 51521003, and the State Key Laboratory of Robotics and Systems (HIT) under Grant SKLRS201619B.

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